

Dehydrogenation of β -Pinene to *p*-Cymene over Platinum-Alumina Catalyst in the Presence of Nitrogen, Hydrogen and Pyridine

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Dehydrogenation of β -pinene has been carried out over platinum-alumina (0.6% Pt) catalyst at 300° in the presence of nitrogen, hydrogen and pyridine. Nitrogen acts as a diluent while hydrogen acts both as a diluent and as a promoter. Pyridine on the other hand functions as a diluent and as a poison. As a result, it affects the formation of different products to different extent. The optimum conditions such as platinum concentration, temperature and contact time for dehydrogenation, hydrogenation and disproportionation reactions were established using cyclohexane, *p*-cymene and cyclohexene, respectively before actually studying the dehydrogenation of β -pinene.

β -PINENE is a bicyclic mono-olefinic monoterpene present together with α -pinene in different proportions in the majority of essential oils derived from coniferae¹. The first quality Indian turpentine oil contains about 10% β -pinene, 4% α -pinene and 50% 3-carene². These bicyclic terpene hydrocarbons undergo initial skeletal isomerization followed by dehydrogenation and disproportionation over dual function catalysts such as chromia and chromia-alumina³⁻⁵.

Platinum-alumina, another important bifunctional catalyst⁶, is increasingly employed in petroleum industry for reforming operations, because of its sustained higher activity and unique selectivity.

Hence, platinum-alumina was chosen to dehydrogenate β -pinene to *p*-cymene, an important aromatic compound that could be oxidised to terephthalic acid⁷ (an intermediate for the manufacture of synthetic fibre, films, etc.), hydrated to camphor⁸ and converted to *p*-cresol via its hydroperoxide⁹. *p*-Cymene can be considered as an alternative source for the manufacture of terephthalic acid which is at present obtained from *p*-xylene.

Experimental

Preparation of materials :

Alumina : Alumina was prepared by hydrolysing aluminium isopropoxide with distilled water¹⁰ with constant and uniform stirring. The precipitated aluminium hydroxide was filtered through a Buchner funnel, washed thoroughly with water, cut into cakes, dried at 120° for 24 hr and activated at 550° in a stream of dry air for 24 hr. It was ground and sieved to -200 mesh size.

Platinum-alumina : Five samples of platinum-alumina catalysts containing 0.1, 0.3, 0.6, 0.9 and

1.4 (confirmed by spectrophotometric analysis¹¹) percent by weight of platinum (Table 1) were prepared by adding the requisite amounts of chloroplatinic acid in water to appropriate quantity of

TABLE 1—DESIGNATION OF DIFFERENT CATALYSTS

Sl. No.	Description	Designation
1	Platinum-alumina (0.1% Pt)	A
2	Platinum-alumina (0.3% Pt)	B
3	Platinum-alumina (0.6% Pt)	C
4	Platinum-alumina (0.9% Pt)	D
5	Platinum-alumina (1.4% Pt)	E

Pure alumina obtained from aluminium isopropoxide was used as support for all the catalysts.

alumina, suspended in water. Each slurry was stirred for 3 hr and dried in a furnace at 120° for 24 hr. After that, the temperature of the furnace was raised slowly to 500° in a period of 2 hr in a current of pure dry hydrogen and kept at this temperature for 8 hr. The activated material, after cooling, was powdered and pelletized to give 4 × 4 mm size pellets.

Pyridine : Pyridine (B.D.H. AnalaR) was refluxed over KOH pellets and distilled through an efficient fractionating column with careful exclusion of moisture and the material distilling at 115.5° was collected. The purity was checked by gas chromatographic analysis.

Nitrogen and hydrogen : Nitrogen and hydrogen (Indian Oxygen Co.) were purified by passing successively through a silica gel drying tower, a tube containing freshly reduced copper turnings at 400° and another silica gel drying tower.

β -Pinene : This was obtained from M/s Fluka and its purity was checked by gas chromatographic analysis.

Cyclohexene: Cyclohexene was prepared by dehydration of cyclohexanol following the procedure described by Vogel^{1,2}.

Apparatus and procedure:

The reactions were carried out at atmospheric pressure in a fixed bed flow type reactor, 50 cm long and 1.5 cm internal diameter (Fig. 1). The reactor was provided with a thermowell reaching into the heart of the catalyst bed. The preheater was made in the form of a spiral wound uniformly round the reactor covering half of its length to ensure complete vapourization of the liquid before entering into the reactor tube. Above the catalyst (5 g) bed, pyrex glass beads (4 mm diameter) were placed to a height of 5 cm. The reactor tube was inserted into a furnace, a cylindrical steel tube of internal diameter 4 cm, coated with a thin layer of asbestos and wound uniformly with nichrome wire, and heated electrically to the requisite temperature.

Nitrogen and hydrogen were carefully metered through a precision Hoke valve and their flow rates were measured with a soap film flow meter. Various partial pressures of pyridine were achieved by mixing it with β -pinene in different proportions.

In order to regenerate and activate the catalyst, it was heated prior to each run for 8 hr in a current of air at 500° until no oxides of carbon were detected in the exit gas. The reactant liquid was fed into the reactor by a constant speed infusion pump. The liquid products collected for the first 15 min of each run covering an hour, were discarded and analysis was made only of the products

collected after this time to ensure attainment of steady state.

The liquid products were identified by gas chromatographic analysis^{1,3} using an AIMIL MK-IIB two metre column of carbowax on chromosorb. For the identification of different compounds, retention times of authentic samples were utilized. Various products identified in this investigation are α -pinene, dipentene, terpinolene, α - and γ -terpinenes, camphene, tricyclene, bornylene, 1-, 3- and 4(8)-menthenes, *cis*- and *trans*-menthanes and *p*-cymene. *p*-Cymene is found to be the final product of the dehydrogenation of β -pinene. The reaction sequence pertaining to the transformations of β -pinene over platinum-alumina catalyst is outlined in Scheme 1.

The surface area of alumina was determined from low temperature adsorption of nitrogen^{1,4} (BET) and the value was found to be 171.7 m²/g. The distribution of acid strength of alumina and total acidity of catalysts C and D were estimated according to the methods of Hirschler *et al*.⁵, by *n*-butylamine titration method and the results are given in Table 2.

The carbon deposited on the surface of the catalyst after the dehydrogenation of cyclohexane was estimated from the amount of CO₂ produced during the regeneration of the catalyst. The percentage of carbon thus estimated is given in Table 3.

Fig. 1. Experimental set up.

TABLE 2—ACIDITY OF THE CATALYSTS

Catalyst	<i>n</i> -Butylamine titres (mequiv/g) using indicators				Total acidity
	Anthraquinone ($pK_a = -8.3$)	Chalcone ($pK_a = -5.7$)	Dicinnamal acetone ($pK_a = -3.0$)	Butter yellow ($pK_a = +3.3$)	
Alumina	0.034	0.056	0.270	0.290	0.650
Catalyst:C	—	—	—	—	0.560
Catalyst:D	—	—	—	—	0.570

TABLE 3—ESTIMATION OF CARBON AFTER DEHYDROGENATION OF CYCLOHEXANE AT 200°

Catalyst	Reaction temp. °C	Weight per cent carbon	
		Oxidised	Reduced
C	300	0.60	0.50
	350	0.70	0.60
D	300	0.60	0.50
	350	0.60	0.50
E	300	0.60	0.60
	350	0.70	0.60

tion of *p*-cymene was done over catalyst C in the temperature range 100-250° and the results are given in Table 6.

 TABLE 6—HYDROGENATION OF *p*-CYMENE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES OVER CATALYST C

Temp. °C	<i>cis</i> -Menthane	<i>trans</i> -Menthane
100	15.0	25.0
150	20.0	24.0
200	8.0	12.0
250	8.0	8.0

Results and Discussion

The transformations of simple hydroaromatics like cyclohexane and cyclohexene were carried out over platinum-alumina catalysts containing varying amounts of platinum and the results are presented in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. The hydrogena-

The effect of particle size on the overall conversion of β -pinene and the effect of reaction time on the formation of *p*-cymene over catalysts C and D respectively were carried out at 300° and the results are given in Table 7. The effect of pretreatment on the dehydrogenation of β -pinene and cyclohexane to *p*-cymene and benzene respectively was investigated over catalysts D and E and the results are recorded in Table 8.

TABLE 4—DEHYDROGENATION OF CYCLOHEXANE TO BENZENE OVER DIFFERENT CATALYSTS AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	Formation of benzene (mole %)				
	A	B	C	D	E
250	15.0	19.0	34.0	37.0	19.0
300	50.0	53.0	73.0	82.0	37.0
350	69.0	76.0	80.0	86.0	69.0

TABLE 5—DEHYDROGENATION AND DISPROPORTIONATION OF CYCLOHEXENE OVER DIFFERENT CATALYSTS AT 250°

Catalyst	Mole %	
	Benzene	Cyclohexane
A	30.0	20.0
C	55.0	25.0
D	54.0	26.0
E	50.0	24.0

 TABLE 7—EFFECT OF PARTICLE SIZE AND REACTION TIME ON THE OVERALL CONVERSION OF β -PINENE AND ON THE FORMATION OF *p*-CYMENE, RESPECTIVELY

Particle size	Catalyst C Conversion (mole %)	Catalyst D	
		Time of reaction (min)	<i>p</i> -Cymene (mole %)
4 x 4 mm	98.1	0-30	44.0
16-30 mesh	98.8	31-45	44.1
180-200 mesh	98.9	46-60	44.1

The effects of partial pressures of nitrogen, hydrogen and pyridine were studied at 300° over catalyst C and the results are plotted in Figs. 2, 3,

TABLE 8—EFFECT OF PRETREATMENT ON THE DEHYDROGENATION OF β -PINENE AND CYCLOHEXANE

Catalyst	Activated in air	Activated then reduced in H ₂ (200 ml/min)	Activated in air	Activated then reduced in H ₂ (200 ml/min)
	Benzene (mole %)		p-Cymene (mole %)	
D	60.1	60.2	38.0	38.2
E	37.1	38.1	35.0	35.2

and 4, J, respectively. The overall conversion of β -pinene and the formation of *p*-cymene are compared in Fig. 5.

Fig. 2. Effect of partial pressure of nitrogen on product distribution.

The dehydrogenation activity of the catalyst increases with increasing concentration of platinum in the catalyst (Tables 4 and 5). The maximum activity occurs around 0.6 to 0.9 per cent platinum. Hence catalyst C at temperature 300° and contact time 0.79 hr was chosen for this investigation.

From the results given in Table 6, it would be evident that the menthanes and menthenes might not be formed by the hydrogenation of *p*-cymene because, (i) the amount of hydrogen evolved during the dehydrogenation of β -pinene is too small and (ii) the temperature is too high to be conducive to hydrogenation. It can therefore be concluded that menthanes and menthenes are formed by the disproportionation of menthadienes (Scheme 1). The disproportionation of cyclohexene to benzene and cyclohexane (Table 5) lends support to the above conclusion.

Fig. 3. Effect of partial pressure of hydrogen on product distribution.

Fig. 4. Effect of partial pressure of pyridine on product distribution.

The constancy in the overall conversion of β -pinene and in the formation of *p*-cymene (the former with changing particle size and the latter

Fig. 5. Effect of partial pressure of β -pinene in the presence of nitrogen, hydrogen and pyridine on the overall conversion of β -pinene and on the formation of *p*-cymene.

with different reaction time intervals as in Table 7) indicates the absence of diffusional effects and the stability of the catalyst during the reaction, respectively. The observed constancy in the formation of aromatics over the oxidised and reduced catalysts can be attributed to non-variation of the valency state of the dehydrogenation component, namely platinum.

With respect to the overall conversion of β -pinene, it could be seen from Fig. 5 that hydrogen produces similar effects as those of nitrogen. This is because hydrogen does not get adsorbed strongly over alumina.

However, the formation of *p*-cymene is more in the presence of hydrogen than in the presence of nitrogen (Fig. 5), due to the promoting action of hydrogen. This promoting action lies in its ability to hydrogenate the unsaturated precursor of coke to saturated compounds which would otherwise lead to the deactivation of the catalyst.

The strong acid sites of alumina (Table 2) can polymerize the menthadienes or isomerize the six membered carbon rings to five membered ring compounds as postulated by Pines *et al.*⁶. The alkylcyclopentenones, resulting from isomerization, polymerize and deposit on the catalyst surface. The strong tendency of C_6 ring compounds to polymerize when in contact with acid catalysts and their ability to form complexes with the transition metals and transition metal ions are well known^{17,18}.

The estimation of carbon after the dehydrogenation of cyclohexane (Table 3) proves the formation

of the precursors of coke. The high yield of *p*-cymene and very low concentration of menthadienes in the products in the presence of hydrogen proves the assumption that hydrogen hydrogenates the precursors of coke and thus maintains the activity of the catalyst at a constant level.

Hydrogen is expected to get adsorbed more strongly over platinum metal sites than nitrogen and thereby decrease the metal concentration available for dehydrogenation; its promoting action adequately compensates its dilution effect.

Pyridine suppresses the overall conversion as well as the formation of *p*-cymene (Fig. 5) and completely eliminates the formation of menthanes and menthenes. The observed decrease in the activity of the catalyst could be attributed to the strong basic nature of pyridine ($pK_b = 8.96$) compared to β -pinene resulting in its preferential adsorption over the acidic sites. Consequently, the number of β -pinene molecules adsorbed over the catalyst decreases progressively with increasing partial pressure of pyridine. As a base, pyridine can also coordinate with platinum metal sites and thus decrease drastically the dehydrogenation and disproportionation reactions of the catalyst.

The concentration of intermediates increases with increasing concentration of pyridine. The weak acid sites of alumina (Table 2), left unaffected by pyridine as pointed out by Parry¹⁹, are still capable of bringing about the isomerization of β -pinene to various intermediates. The primary intermediates like menthadienes and camphene are

not able to undergo further transformations because strong acid sites are not available, being neutralized by pyridine.

Fig. 6 gives a plot of contact time (W/F_A) vs $1/(1-x_A)$ where W is the weight of the catalyst and F_A is the flow rate of β -pinene per gram of the catalyst (Fig. 6). The intercept is unity and from the slope (equal to $C_{A0}k$), as indicated by the rate equation $1/(1-x_A) = (C_{A0}k)t + 1$, the value of the rate constant k was calculated to be 3322 litres gm mole⁻¹hr⁻¹.

Fig. 6. Second order plot.

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